

Matrix remodeling associated 8 or limitrin (MXRA8) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : MXRA8 protein is a receptor for multiple arthritogenic alphaviruses. It has been implicated in progression from leukoplakia to oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC), as a receptor for chikungunya virus, Ross River virus, Mayaro virus, a similarity to a receptor in Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus, bone metabolism, glioma, breast cancer, pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma and prostate cancer. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of MXRA8, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

*ML dicoveries of MXRA8 synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatic, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossil, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecortius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinghieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8)

MXRA8 belongs to V-set domains, which are immunoglobulin (Ig)-like domains resembling the antibody (Ab) variable domain. They are found in diverse protein families, including immunoglobulin light and heavy chains.

Yonezawa et al. [13] reported the molecular cloning of limitrin, a new member of the transmembrane-type immunoglobulin superfamily, since it localized selectively to glia limitans in mouse brain. They demonstrated that the gene product was expressed significantly in mouse brain and primary murine astrocytes and is distributed in the plasma membrane. They found limitrin to be expressed in the spinal cord and in many areas of the brain, but not in the median eminence or subfornical organ (the circumventricular organs), where the blood-brain barrier is lacking and disruption of the blood-brain barrier by cold injury resulted in reduced expression of limitrin. Additionally,

during retrieval from cold injury, the increased expression of limitrin in perivascular endfeet correlated with the recovery of angiogenesis in capillaries within the lesion margins. Their results suggested that limitrin was physically/functionally associated with the blood-brain barrier.

1.3. Roles of MXRA8 in different disease

Bhosale et al. [14] presented an integrative genome-wide analysis to predict the risk of progression from **leukoplakia** to **oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC)** arising in the gingivobuccal complex (GBC). Their integrative analysis revealed several biomarkers that have never or rarely been reported in previous OSCC studies, some of which include amplifications of 1p36.33 (attributable to MXRA8), 3q26.31 (EIF5A2), 9p24.1 (CD274), and 12q13.2 (HOXC9 and HOXC13).

Arthritogenic alphaviruses are a group of enveloped RNA viruses transmitted from mosquitoes to humans and causes debilitating acute and chronic musculoskeletal disease. Zhang et al. [15] identified MXRA8 (cell adhesion molecule), as a **receptor for multiple emerging arthritogenic alphaviruses**, which encompass Ross River, chikungunya, O'nyong nyong viruses and Mayaro. They observed that gene editing of mouse/human MXRA8 resulted in reduced levels of viral infection of cells, while abnormal expression of the same, resulted in increased infection. Further, they found that MXRA8 bound directly to **chikungunya virus** particles and enhanced virus attachment and internalization into cells.

Ross River fever is a mosquito-transmitted viral disease, were the **Ross River virus (RRV)** belongs to the arthritogenic group of alphaviruses, that cause debilitating polyarthritis, rash, and fever. Powell et al. [16] described naturally occurring human mAbs specific to RRV, that were isolated from subjects with a prior natural infection. They found that the mAbs neutralized RRV infectivity in cell culture and blocked infection through inhibition of multiple mechanisms like viral attachment, entry, and fusion. Further, they observed that some of the most potently neutralizing mAbs inhibited binding of RRV to MXRA8.

Mayaro virus (MAYV) is an emerging arbovirus that may cause a debilitating arthritogenic disease. Ribeiro-Filho et al. [17] presented the structure of MAYV at 4.4 Å resolution and found that viral protein interactions led to particle formation which are described together with a hydrophobic pocket formed between E1 and E2 spike proteins and conformational epitopes specific of MAYV. They further described MAYV glycosylation residues in E1 and E2, which might affect MXRA8 host receptor binding.

The homeostasis of **bone metabolism** depends on the coupling and regulation of bone tissue cells. To understand the communication and interaction between bone tissue cells, Qiu et al. [18] performed single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) on the primary human femoral head tissue cells (FHTCs) and identified serine protease 23 (PRSS23) and MXRA8 as bone metabolism-related genes.

Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV) is an alphavirus in the family *Togaviridae* which is highly infectious in aerosol form and a known bio-warfare agent that can cause severe encephalitis in humans. Sharma and Knollmann-Ritschel [19] provide a review of the current understanding of the molecular basis of VEEV pathogenesis

and discuss various types of vaccine candidates. Mosquitoes transmit the neurotropic alphavirus which causes encephalitis and death in humans. Ma et al. [20] identified low-density lipoprotein receptor class A domain-containing 3 (LDLRAD3), belonging to a scavenger receptor superfamily, as receptor for VEEV. They observed that gene editing of mouse/human LDLRAD3 resulted in markedly reduced viral infection of neuronal cells, which was restored upon complementation with LDLRAD3. Basore et al. [21] observed that VEEV engages LDLRAD3 in a manner that is similar to the way that arthritogenic alphaviruses bind to the structurally unrelated MXRA8 receptor, but with a much smaller interface.

Glioma is a highly malignant brain tumor and ferroptosis is a newly recognized process of cell death playing a vital role in cancer biology. Xu et al. [22] identified MXRA8 as a novel prognosis indicator which might be involved in ferroptosis and found that the expression of MXRA8 was significantly higher in glioma compared with normal brain tissue. They further observed that downregulation of MXRA8 elevated the levels of intracellular ferrous iron and lipid peroxidation, accompanied by upregulation of NCOA4 and suppression of FTH1. Also, their co-cultured models of glioma cells and M2 macrophages depicted that MXRA8 knockdown glioma cells alleviated the infiltration of M2 macrophage, and in contrast, the reduced M2 macrophage infiltration generated by MXRA8 could be rescued by FER-1 treatment. Thus their results suggested that MXRA8 promoted glioma progression and highlighted the pivotal role of MXRA8 in ferroptosis and immune microenvironment of glioma.

Breast cancer cells with mesenchymal characteristics, particularly the claudin-low subtype, express extremely low levels of miR-200s. Simpson et al. [23] studied the functional impact of restoring miR-200 expression in a human claudin-low breast cancer cell line MDA-MB-231. They transfected MDA-MB-231 cells with a control vector (MDA-231EV) or the miR-200c/141 cluster (MDA-231c141). Further, they identified down regulation of MXRA8 in MDA-231c141 tumors via RNA sequencing of MDA-231EV and MDA-231c141 tumors. They confirmed higher MXRA8 expression in mammary tumors induced by MDA-231EV cells compared to those induced by MDA-231c141 cells, via qRT-PCR and Western blotting. Also, they observed high levels of MXRA8 protein in metastatic tumor cells found in the lungs. In a first, they studied the implication of MXRA8 in human breast cancer, and their data suggested that miR-200s inhibited growth and metastasis of claudin-low mammary tumor cells in vivo via downregulation of MXRA8 expression.

Cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs), a compartment of the tumor microenvironment are at least of two types of CAFs, that is, cancer-promoting and -restraining CAFs. In a previous study, Meflin was identified Meflin as a candidate marker of cancer-restraining CAFs (rCAFs) in **pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC)**. Ichihara et al. [24] identified MXRA8 expression correlated with Meflin in single-cell transcriptomic analyses of human cancers. Further, their analysis of MXRA8 expression in human PDAC samples showed that MXRA8 was differentially co-expressed with other CAF markers and thus concluded that MXRA8 was a new CAF marker.

Investigation by Miao et al. [25] of MXRA8 in **prostate cancer** showed significant upregulation in the disease as confirmed by PCR and immunohistochemistry. Further, they demonstrated that depletion of MXRA8 reduced the proliferative, invasive, migratory capabilities of PC-3 cells, as well as their ROS generation capacity.

The global re-emergence of alphaviral outbreaks has led to an increase in virus-induced arthralgia and arthritis. These alphaviruses are characterized with acute and/or chronic rheumatic symptoms. Persistent joint pain is a common manifestation of arthropod-borne viral infections and can cause long-term disability. Suchowiecki et al. [26] provide a review of arthritogenic alphavirus infection, at multiple levels of analysis. Studies have reported the identification of MXRA8 as a receptor in the alphaviral replication pathway.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [27] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [28] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option

has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [28].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [29]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [30], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [27] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [27]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [31], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the non-linearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data

may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. MXRA8 related synergies

Note - MXRA8 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of MXRA8 were recorded.

3.1.1. MXRA8 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with MXRA8 showed high rankings - insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF1), CD74 molecule (CD74), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 3 (PTPN3), FRY microtubule binding protein (FRY), carbonic anhydrase 12 (CA12), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 16 (GALNT16), matrix remodeling associated 5 (MXRA5), coronin 2B (CORO2B), olfactomedin 2 (OLFM2), AE binding protein 1 (AEBP1), Kazal type serine peptidase inhibitor domain 1 (KAZALD1), cholinergic receptor nicotinic epsilon subunit (CHRNE), contactin associated protein 1 (CNTNAP1), collagen type XII alpha 1 chain (COL12A1), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), plexin domain containing 2 (PLXDC2), ciliary neurotrophic factor receptor (CNTFR), collagen type XII alpha 1 chain (COL12A1), matrilin 4 (MATN4), RUNX family transcription factor 2 (RUNX2), lysosomal associated membrane protein family member 5 (LAMP5), transmembrane protein 35A (TMEM35A), MBL associated serine protease 1 (MASP1), solute carrier family 6 member 11 (SLC6A11), solute carrier family 14 member 2 (SLC14A2), lymphocyte cytosolic protein 1 (LCP1), forkhead box F2 (FOXF2), semaphorin 6D (SEMA6D), dual oxidase 2 (DUOX2), milk fat globule EGF and factor V/VIII domain containing (MFG8), myosin heavy chain 15 (MYH15), dishevelled associated activator of morphogenesis 2 (DAAM2), dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2), cysteine rich transmembrane

BMP regulator 1 (CRIM1), phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1 (PID1), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), tetraspanin 7 (TSPAN7), myosin IE (MYO1E), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM1), frizzled related protein (FRZB), C1q and TNF related 7 (C1QTNF7), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), 15-hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD), coagulation factor II thrombin receptor like 2 (F2RL2), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), myozenin 3 (MYOZ3), somatomedin B and thrombospondin type 1 domain containing (SBSPON), carbonic anhydrase 3 (CA3), sushi, von Willebrand factor type A, EGF and pentraxin domain containing 1 (SVEP1), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 12A (HSPA12A), PDZ domain containing ring finger 4 (PDZRN4), transmembrane protein 130 (TMEM130), microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4), nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), armadillo repeat containing 4 (ARMC4 / ODAD2), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), serine/threonine kinase 32A (STK32A), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), secretogranin II (SCG2), interleukin 17D (IL17D), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule (CD248), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A / NALF1), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of MXRA8 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t MXRA8 with MXRA8 – > IGF1 /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS MXRA8									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T MXRA8									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
IGF1 - MXRA8	236	262	74	321	CD74 - MXRA8	261	202	294	64
PTPN3 - MXRA8	212	287	275	104	FRY - MXRA8	129	314	212	211
CA12 - MXRA8	203	243	9	310	GALNT16 - MXRA8	155	359	268	210
MXRA5 - MXRA8	328	127	300	199	CORO2B - MXRA8	311	316	261	153
OLFM2 - MXRA8	10	375	280	323	AEBP1 - MXRA8	253	283	61	299
KAZALD1 - MXRA8	176	264	226	253	CHRNE - MXRA8	200	294	240	26
CNTNAP1 - MXRA8	211	350	332	109	COL12A1 - MXRA8	269	276	36	225
C1orf198 - MXRA8	274	250	219	128	PLXDC2 - MXRA8	264	213	367	141
CNTFR - MXRA8	279	382	106	244	COL12A1 - MXRA8	269	276	36	225
MATN4 - MXRA8	35	245	271	297	RUNX2 - MXRA8	186	211	298	300
LAMP5 - MXRA8	1	384	289	391	TMEM35A - MXRA8	283	366	281	9
MASP1 - MXRA8	44	371	225	280	SLC6A11 - MXRA8	280	372	246	217
SLC14A2 - MXRA8	188	204	264	245	LCP1 - MXRA8	371	274	291	123
FOXF2 - MXRA8	232	242	82	260	SEMA6D - MXRA8	94	268	208	239
DUOX2 - MXRA8	46	328	210	307	MFGE8 - MXRA8	240	171	251	246
MYH15 - MXRA8	101	230	296	219	DAAM2 - MXRA8	257	266	224	274
DRD2 - MXRA8	72	301	231	384	CRIM1 - MXRA8	255	308	242	69
PID1 - MXRA8	64	220	277	361	DDAH1 - MXRA8	205	289	217	158
TSPAN7 - MXRA8	299	323	192	255	MYO1E - MXRA8	359	292	228	136
RUNX1 - MXRA8	295	290	207	130	VCAM1 - MXRA8	331	4	371	276
FRZB - MXRA8	378	36	335	313	C1QTNF7 - MXRA8	282	63	376	376
APBB2 - MXRA8	248	233	316	45	HPGD - MXRA8	219	14	304	234
F2RL2 - MXRA8	199	28	343	264	RHOBTB3 - MXRA8	376	121	362	370
EBF1 - MXRA8	322	25	203	270	DACT2 - MXRA8	303	388	323	247
MYOZ3 - MXRA8	348	229	354	271	SBSPON - MXRA8	286	6	352	279
CA3 - MXRA8	315	198	368	369	SVEP1 - MXRA8	287	150	256	284
HSPA12A - MXRA8	364	185	329	312	PDZRN4 - MXRA8	362	261	370	356

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between MXRA8 VS Individual members.

CD74 / PTPN3 / FRY / CA12 / GALNT16 / MXRA5 / CORO2B / OLFM2 / AEBP1 / KAZALD1 / CHRNE / CNTNAP1 / COL12A1 / C1orf198 / PLXDC2 / CNTFR / COL12A1 / MATN4 / RUNX2 / LAMP5 / TMEM35A / MASP1 / SLC6A11 / SLC14A2 / LCP1 / FOXF2 / SEMA6D / DUOX2 / MFGE8 / MYH15 / DAAM2 / DRD2 / CRIM1 / PID1 / DDAH1 / TSPAN7 / MYO1E / RUNX1 / VCAM1 / FRZB / C1QTNF7 / APBB2 / HPGD / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / DACT2 / MYOZ3 / SBSPON / CA3 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / MFAP4 / NNMT / PRRT2 / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C / STK32A / MAP6 / SCG2 / IL17D / SUSD5 / HOXB2 / CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / SERTM1 / EXT1 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / PRKD1 / SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P / LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / MME / FAM180B / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / CYP4F29P / SNX18P13.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic MXRA8 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS MXRA8									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T MXRA8									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
TMEM130 - MXRA8	388	115	388	385	MFAP4 - MXRA8	214	17	347	282
NNMT - MXRA8	382	54	337	350	PRRT2 - MXRA8	226	241	200	202
ENHO - MXRA8	369	203	287	308	ARMC4 - MXRA8	298	69	338	230
CPT1C - MXRA8	334	79	366	309	STK32A - MXRA8	360	59	255	354
MAP6 - MXRA8	304	258	239	185	SCG2 - MXRA8	379	52	391	360
IL17D - MXRA8	245	248	237	70	SUSD5 - MXRA8	363	58	330	268
HOXB2 - MXRA8	333	257	116	226	CD248 - MXRA8	278	392	385	222
DNAH12 - MXRA8	340	99	318	265	P2RY14 - MXRA8	220	322	155	227
SERTM1 - MXRA8	390	60	361	383	EXT1 - MXRA8	201	252	283	47
PLCB1 - MXRA8	221	33	202	266	NTM - MXRA8	339	389	369	366
RGS6 - MXRA8	384	44	390	379	PAPPA - MXRA8	344	35	350	367
TMEM119 - MXRA8	343	284	288	272	OLFML1 - MXRA8	309	152	386	241
DUSP5P1 - MXRA8	326	105	364	251	PRKD1 - MXRA8	352	120	348	298
SHC4 - MXRA8	195	365	381	242	ANKRD20A5P - MXRA8	391	135	373	388
LDLRAD2 - MXRA8	342	70	358	306	PLAC9 - MXRA8	341	49	379	337
NUGGC - MXRA8	319	215	360	252	FAM180A - MXRA8	361	93	378	332
MME - MXRA8	374	48	382	373	FAM180B - MXRA8	389	43	383	359
CLEC9A - MXRA8	377	244	274	243	DLGAP2 - MXRA8	325	86	389	326
MMP17 - MXRA8	353	80	375	281	DLL1 - MXRA8	318	34	230	216
ZNF521 - MXRA8	366	53	320	285	RYR3 - MXRA8	338	369	259	293
RHOT1P2 - MXRA8	387	87	363	319	PLPP4 - MXRA8	215	15	206	331
FAM155A - MXRA8	370	267	334	263	TMEM240 - MXRA8	354	128	269	203
ANKRD20A9P - MXRA8	383	42	324	371	GPX3 - MXRA8	380	56	380	296
HMGB3P7 - MXRA8	357	67	314	258	ANKRD20A11P - MXRA8	372	21	282	347
TENM3 - MXRA8	386	57	310	317	CYP4F29P - MXRA8	385	29	384	378
SNX18P13 - MXRA8	368	46	340	336					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between MXRA8 VS Individual members.

ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of MXRA8-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t MXRA8
IGF1 / CD74 / PTPN3 / FRY / CA12 / GALNT16 ...
MXRA5 / CORO2B / OLFM2 / AEBP1 / KAZALD1 ...
CHRNE / CNTNAP1 / COL12A1 / C1orf198 ...
PLXDC2 / CNTFR / COL12A1 / MATN4 / RUNX2 ...
LAMP5 / TMEM35A / MASP1 / SLC6A11 / SLC14A2 ...
LCP1 / FOXF2 / SEMA6D / DUOX2 / MFGE8 / MYH15 ...
DAAM2 / DRD2 / CRIM1 / PID1 / DDAH1 / TSPAN7 ...
MYO1E / RUNX1 / VCAM1 / FRZB / C1QTNF7 / APBB2 ...
HPGD / F2RL2 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / DACT2 / MYOZ3 ...
SBSPON / CA3 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 ...
MFAP4 / NNMT / PRRT2 / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C ...
STK32A / MAP6 / SCG2 / IL17D / SUSD5 / HOXB2 ...
CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / SERTM1 / EXT1 / PLCB1 ...
NTM / RGS6 / PAPP A / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 ...
PRKD1 / SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P / LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 ...
NUGGC / FAM180A / MME / FAM180B / CLEC9A ...
DLGAP2 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / RHOT1P2 ...
PLPP4 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 ...
HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / CYP4F29P / SNX18P13 MXRA8

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between MXRA8 and Individual members.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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